

COVID-19 Community Surveillance Project: Field Manual

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Overview of the Surveillance Project

The [REDACTED], in partnership with [REDACTED], is conducting community surveillance for COVID-19. Surveys will be administered over the course of two or three select weekends in Winter 2022 – Spring 2022. The purpose of this surveillance is to look at the overall infection rates county-wide, as well as the immune response to a natural infection or to COVID-19 vaccinations. Individuals from randomly selected households in the community will be tested to identify current infections with SARS-CoV-2 virus, measure antibody responses to natural infections or vaccine administration, and they will be asked about their COVID-19 knowledge, attitudes and behaviors. Local municipalities may use this information to guide their COVID-19 response, including recommendations for social distancing, mask wearing, school and business activities, or for the planning of vaccination booster administration to community members. The results of the COVID-19 PCR test will be made available to all participants. [REDACTED] provides support and community referral to those who test positive. Because the laboratory tests for antibody response and genetic sequencing are not FDA-approved, these results will not be provided to individual participants. However, de-identified aggregated data will be made publicly available. Project Field Assistants will go door-to-door to select households for the survey, obtain informed consent from individuals willing to participate, collect anterior nares swabs, and administer questionnaires.

Introduction

The purpose of this document is to summarize the Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for Field Assistants conducting community field work, to serve as the training foundation for field team members. This Field Manual was adapted from [REDACTED] and addresses the following core elements of field work:

1. Ethical Conduct in human subject research
2. HIPAA
3. Field Assistants: Role and Training
4. Field Methods
 - a. Identifying and approaching households
 - b. Obtaining informed consent
 - c. Qualtrics questionnaire administration
 - d. Collecting biological specimens
 - e. Other procedures involving direct contact with project participants
 - f. Departure from household site
 - g. Start-of-Day, End-of-day activities

Ethical Conduct in Human Subjects Research (HSR)

This section of the Field Assistant Guide was developed using [REDACTED], which relied upon the Johns Hopkins School of Public Health Human Subjects Research Ethics Field Training Guide for HSR.

Role of Field Teams in Project Data Collection & Protection

The Field Teams, each comprised of two field assistants, act as ambassadors for the project and are often the first direct contact a participant has with the project. It is important that the Field Team members conduct themselves in a friendly, respectful, and professional manner to ensure a positive impression of the project. It is the responsibility of the Field Team to obtain informed consent from voluntary participants, ensure information is collected and recorded safely and accurately, protect data from loss, and provide accurate information and resources.

Respect

Respect is an important component of research with regards to fellow personnel and for the data. Each member of the field team must show respect for the leaders of the project, fellow field team members, the individual participants, and their community. Additionally, it is imperative that all members show respect for the research methods used to obtain data. During the data collection process, it is critical that information is not only obtained through proper consent but is also recorded accurately, stored safely, and used ethically with respect to the participant. Always be polite whether the person agrees to participate or not.

Voluntary Participation

No individual is required to participate in a research project. Each household approached can refuse to even hear about the project from the Field Team. Individuals interested in participating must meet eligibility criteria and provide informed consent. An individual who agrees to participate can refuse to answer any question, refuse to provide a specimen, and may withdraw from participation at any time. The participant should not be coerced into the study out of a feeling of guilt or fear.

Personal Privacy

Individuals have the right to privacy and must be respected by all team members. It is important that team members do not cause any unnecessary personal embarrassment or discomfort to participants, including respecting the potential participants' personal characteristics. Team members must ensure that privacy is maintained.

Personal Information Protection

Participants risk having their personal information become “public” when they disclose personal information, such as names and contact information, to any project personnel. Personal information is highly confidential and should be protected from public disclosure. Team members should always follow security protocols and data should only be accessible to authorized personnel. Our security protocols include check-in/check-out lists, and secure electronic storage of data. All written records of household sampling and/or consent forms should be given to [REDACTED] at the end of the survey day. Personal health information must be kept private and protected, as governed by HIPAA described in the next section.

HIPAA

The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996 (HIPAA) is a federal law, created to protect sensitive patient health information. This is accomplished through implementation of privacy, security, and breach notification rules. It safeguards electronic transactions of health information. Security in the form of physical, administrative and technical safeguards further maintains the confidentiality, integrity and availability of personal health information. In this project, the COVID-19 polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test results become part of the participant’s health information. The information collected in the Qualtrics questionnaire is not health information and does not contain personally identifiable information. Steps have been taken to protect health information: PCR test results will be de-identified and linked by sample bar-code to the Qualtrics iPad survey data. The PCR test Patient Registration form (PTReg) complies with HIPAA requirements. The Field Assistants play a critical role in ensuring that the bar codes on the collected samples are correctly linked to the questionnaire that each participant completes. Field staff are reminded not share participant information (name or contact information) and not to send personally identifiable information in a non-secure manner. For example, do not text [REDACTED] participant information.

Anonymous reporting to the HIPAA Compliance Line when a security breach may have occurred may be done by calling [REDACTED]. This number is included in the Emergency Contact List (Appendix C).

Field assistants are required to complete the [REDACTED] HIPAA 2021 training [REDACTED]. If you are unable to access this training, contact [REDACTED]. A brief [REDACTED] video on HIPAA will be shown during our in-person training as well. This provides a summary of how HIPAA relates to field work in the local context. Once field assistants complete these trainings, they are required to sign a [REDACTED] Privacy Statement form that will be distributed during our in-person training.

Field Assistants Responsibilities

Field assistants will always work and travel in pairs in the community, wearing their name tags on lanyards. On any single day, each team member will serve in the role of either Sampler or Recorder, described in greater detail below. Field Assistants may decide between themselves which role they would like to take on, and even swap roles their second day in the field if they so wish.

COVID-19 Testing

COVID-19 testing for field staff include PCR testing 2-3 days prior to their field work (this can be as part of regular [REDACTED] surveillance). Depending upon [REDACTED] COVID guidelines at the time of the survey, an antigen home test may be required the morning of their field work. If a home test is required, these will be distributed during the in-person training. A [REDACTED] supplemental or surveillance test is also recommended the week following the survey.

Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

All field assistants are required to wear medical procedure masks (provided) and maintain social distance with members of the community. Additionally, when assisting with nasal swab collection or handling material collected from participants, the Sampler must wear a face shield, protective nitrile gloves, and a disposable lab coat outside of their own winter coats.

Appropriate donning and doffing of PPE are demonstrated in the training videos, and will be practiced during the in-person training. De-gloving and appropriate sanitizing should be done in between household visits, according to the methods summarized in this manual, and reviewed in the in-person training. Under exceptional circumstances in which engagement with a participant may be prolonged (greater than 10 minutes), within close proximity (< 6 ft), and participants are not wearing masks, it is reasonable for Field Assistants to politely ask whether participant would be willing to don a mask, and to provide these on an as-needed basis. Similarly, if at any time a participant would like to don a mask, there will be extras available to provide them.

Sampler

The Sampler will be the one who assists consenting participants in the collection of nasal swab samples, and as such, will be the one who dons and doffs the additional PPE described above during the brief period of time when samples are being collected. The sampler will be the one who, throughout the day, handles all of the 'dirty' materials including samples and waste.

Responsibilities of the Sampler include

- guides participant through nasal swab collection while remaining appropriately distanced

- works with Recorder to ensure that the sample tube scanned into Patient Registration is the tube used for sample collection
- collects all waste (swab wrappers, etc), and returns it to the vehicle biohazard waste bin
- remains in charge of small transport cooler box, storing and replenishing
- follows appropriate sanitization of hands, face shields, and disposable gowns

Recorder

The Recorder will help navigate the team to the appropriate neighborhood, and will be involved in all aspects of record-keeping during the survey. This includes maintenance of the Housing Unit (HU) tracking sheet (Appendix A), Tube tracking sheet (Appendix B), and administration of the Qualtrics survey questionnaire using iPads. HUs are defined below.

Responsibilities of the Recorder include

- records households that are approached on the HU tracking sheet
- scans the appropriate tube, confirming that the same tube is used for sample collection
- tracks tubes on the Tube tracking sheet
- administers questionnaire, including setting up MiFi units and iPads
- keeps track of all forms
- replenishes tote bags with survey materials needed for next Housing Unit (HU)

If the Recorder needs to assist the Sampler with some tasks that involve handling ‘dirty’ materials (samples, waste), the Recorder will don gloves or additional appropriate PPE, and will follow the appropriate sanitation process described later. Both individuals will be trained in proper sterile technique in order to ensure the integrity of the samples, as well as the safety of all involved. It is recommended to keep a clean pair of gloves in the tote bags at all times for whenever this becomes necessary.

The Recorder will work together with Sampler to ensure the tube bar code number is accurately reflected in the Patient Registration form for the correct participant. This is done by scanning the QR code on the tube the Sampler has organized for the participant, and double-checking the tube number against the entry appearing in the PTReg Form. The importance of this cannot be over-emphasized. The only way that the information in the questionnaire is linked to the sample is through the process of scanning the bar code number. If there are multiple samples being collected at any one household, then each participant’s questionnaire must be linked to the correct bar code number.

Attire

Field Teams should wear comfortable weather- and work-appropriate (i.e., professional) clothing when interacting with members of the community and representing the project. Closed-

toed shoes that are comfortable to walk in are highly recommended. Professional attire excludes wearing shirts with political slogans or advertising sports teams or companies. In inclement weather, additional attire (boots, winter or rain coats, hats, scarves and gloves) may be necessary to protect from the elements. Hand warmers will be provided during colder months. As mentioned above, as part of their attire, name tags on lanyards will be provided to each team member to display while they are working in the community.

Use of Fleet Garage Vehicle (Drivers only)

Field Assistants will use [REDACTED]-owned Fleet Garage vehicles for their field work. Please note that samples MAY NOT be transported in personal vehicles at any time. A US Driver's License is required in order to drive Fleet vehicles. Prior to driving a Fleet Garage vehicle, field assistants must complete both a registration and a driver release form (links are provided below). As soon as you are hired and have a [REDACTED], you should begin this process. It may take up to 72 hours or more before your approval comes through. Fleet Service policy manual may be found here: [REDACTED]. For any questions regarding Fleet Garage vehicle registration, please contact [REDACTED] during regular business hours on [REDACTED].

Fleet Garage User Registration:

[REDACTED]

Fleet garage Driver Release Form (must complete Registration form first before this one):

[REDACTED]

Car & Motor Safety

Team drivers must follow rules and regulations of the road, as they are entrusted with the safety of their fellow team members, as well as the safety of others in the community. Please remember to always wear seat belts and remain masked at all times

Additional information about the Fleet Garage, including the signing out and returning of fleet cars, is provided below, in the sections describing Start-of-Day and End-of-Day procedures. Please read additional COVID-19 precautions and guidelines as applicable to use of fleet vehicles here:

[REDACTED]

In case of an accident, a team member should report information in this order:

1. Emergency safety calls depending upon need, such as 911 for ambulance, and/or police

2. Report to your Supervisor, [REDACTED], available by phone/text (see Emergency Contact List laminated sheet; Appendix C). [REDACTED] will help complete steps 3 and 4 below.
3. Complete EHS Incident Reporting (within 24 hours of the incident):
[REDACTED]
4. Report to Fleet Garage by email at [REDACTED] as soon as possible (see [REDACTED] in vehicle for additional information)

Situational Awareness & Group Communication

Situational awareness is important when working in the community. Members of the Field Team should be aware of their surroundings at all times. Additionally, please ensure the vehicle is locked at all times. If the Field Team finds a particular house or situation uneasy, please immediately skip the location and contact [REDACTED]. Remember to stay calm, polite, and considerate. Prior to going out into the community, it is strongly recommended to have an established communication line as well as personnel safety measures put into place. As teams, we will remain in communication with each other throughout the day using WhatsApp or text messaging. We recommend downloading the RAVE Guardian App ([REDACTED]) and being aware of any personal safety measures on your mobile phone (e.g., iPhones have an Emergency SOS feature). These will be discussed in our In-person training, and an Emergency Contact List (Appendix C) will be made available to teams (copies will be taped to the back of clipboards). [REDACTED] Police and [REDACTED] Police will be made aware of our teams going into the field, and will know what you are doing. You may also contact them if necessary.

News Media

Our February surveillance weekend will be announced to the community with a press release. While announcing our presence prior to the surveillance weekend will be beneficial, it may also result in active media coverage while in the field. Field Teams are not allowed to speak to the media directly or be filmed actively engaging with members of the community. Privacy and protection of participants is critical. If a Field Team is approached by news media, the Field Team must immediately stop their work and notify [REDACTED] as soon as possible. Inform the news media that no statements are to be made and that the Field Team is unable to conduct their job in the presence of the news media. A handout (press release copy) will be provided to teams to distribute in the event you are approached by news media (Appendix D).

Field Assistant Training

Field assistants will complete approximately 12 hours of training. This is comprised of both on-line and a 3-hour in-person training.

On-Line Training

The on-line component of training will include [REDACTED] videos (accessible using [REDACTED]), HIPAA training, Human Subjects Review training, as well as select other videos and reading materials that review appropriate Communication Strategies. All on-line training and associated links will be posted up in a Canvas site created for Field Assistant training. Listed below is a summary of all of the on-line videos to complete, with the exception of those still to be made available through Canvas.

To track your progress [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

- **HR300 Responsibility [REDACTED] 2021 45 mins.**
- [REDACTED] - **HERO Act Designation of COVID-19 as an Airborne Infectious Disease Compliance Training 15 mins.**
- [REDACTED]: **Donning/Doffing PPE for COVID Testing at [REDACTED] Collection Sites 4 mins.**
Donning/doffing PPE: gown, gloves (double gloved) and face shield
- [REDACTED]: **COVID Swabbing Procedures at [REDACTED] Collection Sites 4 mins.** Swabbing procedure at CU collection site
- [REDACTED]: **Registration of COVID Participants at [REDACTED] Collection Sites 20 mins.** This video provides info relevant to [REDACTED] patient registration (PTReg). Much of the information does not apply to our survey registration process. See additional information in Field Manual on PTReg process for our system using iPads in HUs. This will be reviewed in the in-person training.
- [REDACTED] - **Bloodborne Pathogens for COVID-19 Testing Sites 15 mins.** Developed for all personnel handling human skin, eye mucous membrane from human blood OR potentially infectious materials.
- [REDACTED] – **DOT Hazardous Materials Transportation-- Materials of Trade ([REDACTED]) 20 mins.**
Transportation of exempt hazardous materials.
- [REDACTED] – **Health and Safety Basics - Department of Transportation Materials of Trade 30 mins.**
- [REDACTED] – **DOT Class 6.2 Infectious Substances Class B Certification (2 parts; 45 mins ea= 90 mins total).**

[REDACTED] **HIPAA 2021 Training 45 mins.** Must be assigned to field staff by [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

CITI IRB Training—

(8 Modules available in Audio-Visual or Classic style (reading); 15-30 mins / module (a little longer for AV version): **Approx 3 hours total.** Find at this link:

[CITI IRB \(Human Participant Research\) Basic Training](#) Stage 1—Basic Course, 8 modules.

Use the “course selection” (Show Courses for .. [REDACTED]) to sign up for the IRB course. You will answer NOT AT THIS TIME or NO to all questions except Question 1 (IRB Training), then submit.

Additional Canvas On-line Training: ~ 2 hours

A Canvas site contains communication training materials (LARA). The on-line portion of Canvas is estimated to require approximately 2 hours. Additionally, there is a calendar with dates and locations of in-person trainings and upcoming surveys.

In-Person Training

A three-hour in-person training will focus on field assistant engagement with research methods, (such as donning and doffing of PPE, nose swab technique, use of hotspot with iPad, scanning practice tubes and familiarizing yourselves with the on-line Patient Registration form, and Qualtrics questionnaire administration) as well as opportunities to demonstrate application of principles from the on-line training. There will be both discussion and hands-on activities, covering the following in greater detail:

- Field Methods Powerpoint, demonstrations, & Hands-on practice
- Communication: Difficult encounters; putting LARA technique into practice
- HIPAA: Short video, Discussion of Application to our surveillance project, Privacy Form
- Safety Review (Environmental Health and Safety team, Crime Prevention team, and Emergency Contact List [Appendix C] review)
- Team activities: Communication Review/Discussion/Practice Scripts

Identifying and approaching households (Housing Units; HUs)

House selection process

A 2-stage cluster sampling design is used to identify a random sample of housing units and participants. A housing unit (HU) is a home, apartment, or other group of rooms that are occupied by an individual or group of people. Throughout this Field Manual, the terms HU and household are used interchangeably.

The first stage involves random selection of 15 US Census clusters, with probability proportional to size (█████ completes this step). The second stage happens in the field and involves random selection of 8 housing units (HU) within each cluster, using systematic sampling. Systematic sampling involves contacting HUs at regular intervals within the cluster. The sampling interval (k) is calculated by dividing the total number of HU's in the cluster by 8. Teams will be provided with two maps, one for each of the neighborhoods they have been assigned. Maps will show a starting point (i.e., an address) from which they shall start in the neighborhood, going to every k th house in the cluster. The top of the map provides the value for k , along with additional identifying information about the neighborhood. Only HUs located within each neighborhood cluster are included in the sampling interval (Figure 1).

Systematic selection of households is vital to the sampling methodology. Teams should not select households by convenience (e.g., do not include a person outside an unselected home who indicates to Field Assistants that they wanted to participate). Teams should revisit houses in which no one answers or no adult was home at the time of their visit. Revisiting sampled households where the door was not originally answered by an adult improves the representativeness of the sample. Households in which no one answers after 2 visits, or refuses to participate, are replaced.

As the Field Team works through their assigned cluster, the following items should be kept in mind (Figure 2 provides a flow chart that summarizes these criteria):

- Do not count houses that are clearly vacant. These are skipped
- Do not count group housing, such as dormitories, nursing homes, or adult care homes. These are skipped
- Do not count businesses, schools, offices, places of worship, etc. These are skipped
- If 8 house units are not selected after the first pass through the cluster due to refusals to participate, proceed through a second round of the cluster with a new starting point (e.g. move 1-2 houses down the interval and begin again) to reach your target number of 8 participating households.
- During subsequent passes of the cluster, consult the Housing Unit tracking sheet to avoid those units that have already been visited or excluded, until 8 housing units are recruited.

Navigating to the neighborhoods and parking the fleet garage vehicle

Each team will be surveying two different neighborhoods, A and B. The plan is to start with Neighborhood A on Saturday morning (approx. 10a – 12:30p), and then go to Neighborhood B Saturday afternoon (~ 1-3:30p). On Sunday, this order will be reversed allowing the opportunity to visit neighborhoods at different times. Keep this in mind when deciding what time to schedule a return to a non-responding household for a second attempt.

Teams will be provided two maps; each with a starting point. Teams will drive to their first neighborhood (on Saturday, Neighborhood A) and select a place to park the vehicle. Depending on the neighborhood, it is possible the team will have to relocate the parked vehicle multiple times throughout the morning to ensure the vehicle is nearby for replenishing materials. Please remember to ensure you lock vehicle at all times. Pay attention to parking signs in case it will be necessary to the move vehicle after 2 hours. Most places for weekend parking in [REDACTED] will be free. If the team needs to park in a spot that requires payment, please retain receipts (screenshots of the meter, garage ticket receipt, bank statement or credit card bill) for reimbursement. This process will require completion of a fillable [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]. Please do this at your earliest convenience within approximately a week following the survey.

Housing Unit (HU) Tracking Sheet

The Recorder will track the team's progress on their Housing Unit tracking sheet (Appendix A) for that neighborhood. When a HU is selected to approach, the team Recorder writes the address of the HU on the second page of the tracking sheet. For homes that do not wish to participate, they will thank them for their time, and make a record of this in the tracking sheet they don't return to this home a second time.

If no one is home, they will leave a door hang (Appendix E) and record this, with the intent to return to this home once more before replacing it with another HU. If a minor answers the door, they may know of a good time when an adult will be back. In general, it is suggested not to return sooner than 2 hours from the initial visit unless you learn otherwise. Leave door hangs with date of visit, and date and approximate time of revisit, clearly written with a Sharpie pen, and keep track of those HUs that the team will try to revisit on the HU tracking sheet. Teams should use their discretion as to date and approximate time to schedule return visits, keeping in mind a) the goal to obtain as many samples as possible from the HUs that are initially selected to participate, and b) the distance to drive between neighborhoods, so schedule your time accordingly. It is possible some community members will call [REDACTED] and request a specific time that works best for them after they've read the door hang; should this happen, [REDACTED] will inform the team via WhatsApp or text message.

Tracking sheets are an important component in the data collection process. Data entered in the tracking sheet are used to calculate response rates, which are used, in part, to determine the representativeness of the sample population. The team recorder is responsible for completing the tracking sheet. It is critical that the Field Teams accurately and completely document the outcome of every selected HU approached. This includes documenting selected HUs that declined to participate, no one answered the door, or were excluded (reasons for exclusion(s))

are recorded in the HU tracking sheet). Recorder also tracks the numbers of participants who completed the various components of the survey (i.e., those who completed the PTReg, Qualtrics questionnaire, and nasal samples). These numbers may differ if someone changes their mind about participating part-way through the survey.

Follow the instructions below for filling in the HU Tracking Sheet (Appendix A):

Approach of Housing Unit: record if anyone answered the door.

- If the HU was answered by an adult individual ≥ 18 years, Field Team marks 'Door was Answered'.
- In the event an individual < 18 years of age answers the door and no adult is present, the Field Team marks the attempt as 'No Adult Home After 1st Visit'. The Field Team leaves a door hanger and follows revisit protocol by returning for a 2nd attempt later that day, in order to speak with an adult individual ≥ 18 years.

HU declines to participate: check the corresponding refusal box, and put slashes (/) in the number of PTRegistrations completed, questionnaires completed, and nasal swabs collected spaces for that HU. The team then proceeds to the next kth HU.

HU is excluded: If the HU is interested in participating but does not meet the eligibility criteria, check the appropriate box for exclusion reason. Put slashes in the number of PTRegistrations completed, questionnaires completed, and nasal swabs collected spaces for that HU.

At least one member of the HU agrees to participate: Record the total number of 'PT Registrations completed,' 'Questionnaires Completed' and 'Nasal Swab Collected' for the HU in the spaces indicated. These numbers may differ if someone withdraws from the survey after completing part of it. If there are questions about a participant declining part of the survey procedures, contact [REDACTED].

Approaching HUs

The way you approach HUs plays a key role in the success of this project. HUs were randomly selected, and it is imperative we do our best to engage those HUs selected with a positive experience. The best possible outcome is to obtain participation from as many of the initial HUs approached as possible. We will respect household decisions and move on if HUs are unwilling to participate. For this reason, great care must be taken in how we approach HUs.

Field teams should **always approach homes with safety in mind**. When approaching households, consider the following accessibility conditions:

- Housing Units (HUs) with high gates and fences that cannot be seen around can be excluded from interval count out of concerns for safety

- Never enter a fenced in yard with an unleashed dog. Exclude these HUs
- HUs with signs such as ‘No Trespassing’ or ‘No Solicitation’ or other hostile signage should be excluded from the interval count.
- Additional considerations to be aware of are long driveways and corner lots. Houses may be difficult to see. You don’t want to miss them. In inclement weather, drives may not be plowed or may be icy.

Field Teams should be mindful that there may be anxiety and/or fatigue in the community driven by the pandemic. Residents may be anxious or hesitant to respond when they are approached by masked strangers. Furthermore, many in our community may be tired of anything extra asked of them having to do with COVID-19. It is critical to navigate each situation tactfully and respectfully.

Once any HU is approached, the first 30 seconds are key to establishing legitimacy. It is always a good idea to try to connect with the person who answers the door. Consider ways to do this. This will be practiced more during the in-person training. It is important to bear in mind there will be many different mindsets among the population.

When approaching households, the Field Team should:

- Respectfully present themselves at the door of the randomly selecting housing unit while maintaining a socially distanced measure of 6 feet (2 meters). All interactions should occur outside.
- Introduce themselves clearly and in a friendly manner.
- Present identification badges.

Before you approach the household, it is a good idea to have your MiFi turned on and connected to the iPad. More information on MiFis is provided below in the sections on Verizon Orbic Hotspot MiFi connecting to iPad, and Troubleshooting the MiFi Device.

Either team member (Recorder or Sampler) can take the lead on communication with households, or they can take turns. Once introductions have been made, a team member asks if the resident(s) has time to hear about an important COVID-19 public health project. If the resident agrees to hear more information, a team member explains the purpose of the public health project and broadly explains what is expected of them if they choose to participate.

- If someone <18 years old answers the door, ask to speak to an adult (18 years or older). If you are unsure of someone’s age, ask if they are 18 or older.
- Provide the purpose: To estimate how many people in the community have COVID-19 infections right now, had infections in the past, or have immunity from vaccination. Also, to identify risk factors for infection (such as traveling, or eating in restaurants).

- First, participants will complete the Patient Registration Form (PTReg)
- Then they will complete the Qualtrics questionnaire
- Finally, they will work with the Sampler to collect their nasal swab (non-painful front of nose swab).
- Pay attention to the choice of language used. This is not a research project; it is a public health survey in partnership with the Health Department and [REDACTED].
- Let participants know how long the process takes (15-20 minutes for adults, 5-10 minutes for children because of a shorter questionnaire). It is important to provide as accurate an estimate of the time requirement as possible, to ensure participants will be able to complete the process. If they prefer you return at another time, record this and let them know you will try to return at a mutually agreed upon day and time.
- If there is a language barrier and no one 18 years of age or older speaks English, thank them, and move on. Record the language spoken, if known, on the second page of the Housing Unit tracking sheet for that neighborhood.

Treat potential participants respectfully and work to put the individual at ease when speaking with them. The Field Team should address legitimacy concerns and be prepared to answer any questions. Potential participants may have questions regarding the project or other non-related research questions. Always respond to questions with accurate information. If an answer is unknown, direct the participant to appropriate resources and information sites as determined in training. If the question demands immediate attention, contact [REDACTED]. Their contact numbers are on the Emergency Contact List (Appendix C).

When engaging with a household member, the Field Team should stress that the personal information (name, address, phone number, email) the participant provides is protected and not disseminated outside the purpose of identification of the sample to the lab. PCR test results are shared with [REDACTED] Health Department, whereas individual antibody results are not shared with the Health Department). Names are removed before lab results are shared with [REDACTED] personnel. Additionally, the Team can demonstrate what the nasal swab process looks like and reiterate that the process does not cause pain. If the potential participant agrees to participate, the Field Team determines eligibility.

Script for Approaching HUs

An example script of what to say when approaching households is provided in Appendix F, Script 1. You do not need to say this script word for word. You may develop your own language for how you would like to greet the household member(s) and provide an overview of the study.

Returning to HUs a 2nd time

In the event that no one answers the door of a Housing Unit (HU), the Field Team leaves behind a door hang (Appendix E) which announces the team's presence in the neighborhood and that their household was selected at random for participation, and states an effort will be made to contact the HU again. There is a space on the door hang for the Recorder to mark the date of initial visit, and date and approximate time of a return visit (e.g., "afternoon" or "approximately 2-4 pm"). The Field Team attempts to revisit the HU a second time, either later that same day, or they may choose to return on the following day at the times they plan to be in the neighborhood (remember you visit each neighborhood both days). It is best to allow ample time for individual(s) to return to the HU (2 hours minimum) before revisiting.

Make sure to check the revisit box on the Housing Unit tracking Sheet as you go. If there is no response after the second visit, mark 'No Adult Home After 2nd Visit' and move on to the next kth HU for your sample. If you have gone around the entire cluster and identified every kth house, and there is still time to visit more HUs, you can select a new starting point and go to every kth house to find replacements. If this occurs, the recorder should indicate on the neighborhood map the new starting point, and on the HU tracking sheet those HUs that are replacements and that were selected from a new starting point. Note that when starting from a new point, you do not count the HUs you already sampled as you count to the next kth house.

Inclement weather

In the event that it is raining or snowing out, please dress accordingly. Remember that Field Assistants may not enter participant's houses and should not approach secluded private areas such as garages or sheds. If there is a covered porch, or other open covered area in the front of the house (visible from the street) and respondents agree to these places, Field Assistants may conduct the survey there. Also, Field Assistants may allow participants to take an iPad into their house briefly to complete the questionnaire indoors. When problems arise, please discuss potential solutions with [REDACTED].

Determining eligibility

Prior to obtaining consent, conducting the questionnaire, and collecting the sample, the Field Team determines the eligibility of the participant (Figure 2). Exclusion criteria may preclude respondents from participating. For initial screening, we must ask whether anyone in the Housing Unit is currently in isolation (recently tested positive for COVID-19 and placed in isolation by the health department), or in mandatory quarantine (MQ; determined by the health department to be a contact to someone who has tested positive, and as a consequence placed in quarantine). Households with any individuals in isolation or in MQ will not be included in the survey. This is recorded on the Housing Unit tracking sheet. Field assistants thank the household and move on.

Eligibility is based on the following inclusion criteria:

- The selected HU is their usual place of residence (they live there for more than six months during the calendar year OR the individual is staying at the selected HU and they have no other usual place of residence)
- The individual is capable of and is age-appropriate to provide informed consent
- The individual is capable of communicating with the Field Team and demonstrates a clear understanding of what is expected for participation
- The individual can read and understand English in order to complete and sign the informed consent form, follow instructions for collecting nasal swabs, and complete the Qualtrics questionnaire on an iPad.

There is no need to ask every person directly and explicitly if the eligibility criteria apply to them, or for the potential participant to provide documentation such as a lease agreement or identification card. The Team needs to use best judgement to evaluate:

- If an individual is capable of consent
- If an individual is age-appropriate to provide informed consent
- If an individual is capable of completing the questionnaire

Reminder: Individuals who **do not qualify** to participate include:

- People in isolation or mandatory quarantine (the entire household is excluded)
- Individuals who are unwilling to provide a nasal swab sample (they only want to fill out the survey)
- Individuals for whom the HU is not their usual place of residence, as defined above. For example, neighbors, guests, babysitters, landlords, etc
- People residing in nursing homes, assisted living residences
- Minors unable to obtain parental consent at the time of the visit
- Children under the age of 2
- Children who are in foster care or are wards of the state
- Individuals who cannot understand and read English.

Informed Consent

The purpose of informed consent is to convey adequate study information to potential participants regarding study purpose, study procedures, study risk, and study benefits. Informed consent is not a single event. Throughout the duration of the survey, it is the responsibility of the Field Team to ensure that the participant is truly agreeing to participate in the study without coercion and with full understanding of the intent of the study.

This ongoing process begins with the team members explaining the purpose of the study and what participation looks like. It is important to speak slowly and clearly and to answer any questions or concerns that the participant may have. Explain the risks (anonymity of data can never be guaranteed but we have processes in place to limit access to data) and benefits (help the community understand the level of infection and immunity). True informed consent cannot be obtained if the participant does not understand what is being asked of them. It is critical to present the study information in a language that is easy to understand.

Then the participant is asked to review two informed consent forms and electronically sign or consent to the documents. The first informed consent form is from [REDACTED] for COVID-19 PCR testing. The second informed consent form is at the beginning of the Qualtrics questionnaire and is consent for antibody testing and questionnaire data collection. Team members should provide enough time for potential participants to read over the information and to ask questions. If a potential participant seems agitated or has negative body language, let them know that they may elect not to participate at any time. If you are unsure how to proceed, contact [REDACTED] for further guidance.

Informed consent may occur through consenting adults (participants 18 years of age or older) who agree to participate, child assent with parental consent, or adult assent with consent of their legal representative (for adults with challenged capacity). Minors under the age of 18 must have their parent or legal guardian provide consent for their participation, and must be asked about their willingness to participate (assent) after the process of their participation is explained to them in lay terms.

Vulnerable Populations

Vulnerable populations within a community include children, pregnant women, mental-disabled persons, and economically and educationally disadvantaged persons. Members of vulnerable populations may need extra attention and careful consideration when approached to participate in a research project, as they may have challenges in understanding the information and may have difficulty in providing informed consent. For example, children need “extra protection” by having parents aid in making decisions regarding study participation. Adults with dementia or other mental impairments may have difficulty providing true informed consent. It is vital that the Field Team follows the rules and eligibility criteria when enrolling vulnerable populations as they often cannot make decisions for themselves. In this situation, an authorized caregiver or other proper legal representative must be available at the time of the study participation. For individuals with challenged capacity, the adult is asked for their assent or agreement to participate and their legally authorized representative (i.e., caregiver or guardian) will fill out the consent forms.

Obtaining informed consent

Once residents agree to hear more about the project and they are determined to be eligible, you are ready to obtain informed consent. As stated previously the purpose of informed consent is to convey predetermined adequate study information to potential participants. This includes:

- Purpose of the project
- Steps for participation
- Address any participation risks or concerns
- Project benefits

After these are explained, team members should assess the capacity of consent for that individual before having the potential participant sign the form. Assessing capacity can simply be addressed by asking the potential participant to repeat back to the Field Team a summary of what they believe participation involves. For example, you may ask, “I know I’ve just given you a lot of information and I want to make sure I’ve covered everything correctly. Before I continue, would you tell me your understanding of what we’re asking you to do?”

Information to consider during the consent process:

- Be sure to ask if they have any questions or concerns before giving the individual the Patient Registration form (on the iPad) to read, review, and consent to
- Let individuals know they will be given a copy of the Study Consent / Executive Summary in the Participant Leave-Behind Print Materials packet, as it contains pertinent study contact information should they wish to ask additional questions later on
- In the event there is no cellular service to connect iPads to the MiFis, individuals may still provide consent by 1) completing a paper Patient Registration form, and 2) completing the consent process using the off-line Qualtrics App. The data collected will be synced to our database once wifi access on the iPad is re-established.

Every adult individual ≥ 18 years and with capacity reads and agrees to the consent page on the Patient Registration Form and the Qualtrics questionnaire. For individuals with challenged capacity, the field assistants should ask them if they assent (agree) to participate in the study, and request that their legally authorized representative (LAR) reads and agrees to the consent pages. The LAR is a person (e.g., caregiver or spouse) who has the legal authority to approve participation for the individual who has the LAR. Teams can ask adults if they understand what they are asked to do in the survey and if they are able to provide consent. If at any time the Team is unsure of the capacity for approval in a particular situation, they should contact [REDACTED] for further guidance, or skip that individual.

Consent considerations when obtaining consent for minors to participate

With respect to minors, individuals <18 years, consent is required of the parent or legal guardian in both the Patient Registration form and the Qualtrics questionnaire. In addition to obtaining parental consent, the minor should be asked to provide assent, after a team member explains participation in appropriate language. Appropriate language will vary depending on the child's age, ranging from a simple description of the child's involvement to a complete description of the project and their participation in lay language. Verbal assent (agreement) should be obtained from all children. Figure 3 summarizes this process.

Although age is used as the primary criteria in determining an appropriate means of obtaining assent, factors such as literacy and mental development must also be considered. The need for flexibility in the methods for obtaining assent from children is universally recognized. Because a single method of obtaining assent may not be appropriate for all potential participants, Field Assistants may need to be prepared to use different approaches with different participants. As in any consent process, the primary concern is that the participant is able to understand the explanation that is presented.

During the informed consent process, it is important to check in with potential participants to answer any questions they may have. At any time, if a minor dissents despite parental or guardian approval, the minor dissent is respected. They should not be expected to participate.

All minors <18 years require parental consent in order to participate. Informed consent must be obtained PRIOR to sample collection and questionnaire administration.

- Children 2 years of age or older are allowed to participate. The Field Team should use their best judgment in assessing the children's willingness to participate.
- If the child is adamant or showing extreme distress, the child should not participate.

Script for Obtaining Informed Consent

An example script of what to say when obtaining Informed Consent is provided in Appendix F, Script 2. You do not need to say this script word for word. You may develop your own language for how to explain the study, discuss benefits and risks, and obtain consent.

PTReg and Qualtrics Questionnaire Administration using iPads

██████████ Patient Registration (PTReg)

Questionnaire responses are linked to the bar code on the participant's sample tube. For this reason, we must go through the household members one by one, completing all steps (PTReg, Qualtrics questionnaire, sample collection) before moving on to the next participant.

The PCR testing of all samples will be conducted by the ██████████ (CCTL) located on ██████████. This laboratory has authorization to do the testing through ██████████ licensure. All samples will be scanned into ██████████ Patient Registration System (PTReg; process described below). This will enable PCR test results to be reported back to participants through ██████████ Patient Portal.

Before registering participants, make sure the participants understand the procedures: PCR test registration, questionnaire, and providing a nasal swab. If for any reason participants decline one of these procedures, please check with ██████████ before continuing. This will be considered on a case-by-case basis.

Note that for any given HU, the final counts for how many completed the questionnaire, the sampling, and PT Reg may vary depending upon which portions of the survey participants agree to complete.

Verizon Orbic Hotspot MiFi connecting to iPad

Each team has an iPad and a Verizon Orbic Jetpack MiFi hotspot. iPads should already be configured to connect to the MiFi devices. The Recorder will make sure the MiFi is on (press the power button and hold for 3 seconds until the Welcome logo is displayed; Figure 4), and on the iPad, navigate to the iPad settings to confirm that it is connected to the MiFi's wifi SSID network, similar to 'Verizon-RC400L-xy' (Figure 5).

PT Registration—Scanning the tube QR code using iPad camera

Patient registration is done by scanning the sample tube QR code with the iPad camera. This brings up a Patient Registration form that shows the bar code number of the scanned tube as the Specimen ID. Upon completion of the Patient Registration form, a link appears that connects to our Qualtrics questionnaire. The Sample ID of the questionnaire is auto-populated with the patient registration number assigned to their sample tube, along with other demographics. All Field Assistants will practice PT Registration during the In-class training, using practice tubes.

First, the Recorder opens the camera App on the iPad and scans the QR code of the sample tube (Figure 6). This is the tube the Sampler is preparing for the participant. **Sampler should place this tube by itself into the Styrofoam holding rack after scanning so it is not confused with other tubes.** Upon scanning the QR code, a Safari link will appear, directing you to [REDACTED] patient registration portal (link visible in Figure 6). Upon clicking the Safari link, the [REDACTED] PTReg form will open up (Figure 7), and you are asked to type in the pin (15777) into the space above the green line (visible in Figure 7). This PIN number is conveniently taped to the top of the iPad for easy access.

The first screen that appears after you click on the Safari link is shown in Figure 8. This shows the sample tube's bar code number entered as Specimen ID. Click 'Register Sample' to register the participant's sample tube. You are now ready to pass the iPad to the participant to type in the information requested on the PTReg form. If anyone asks, tell them to ignore that it mentions Saliva Collection; remind them we are collecting nasal swabs.

The PTReg form asks for specific information such as first and last name, date of birth, gender, race, ethnicity, and contact information including phone, email and local address. By providing their email address (optional), their PCR results will be emailed to them. For the question about Affiliation to Organization/Employer, they should select 'Other' which is at the bottom of the drop-down pop-up box. A screen will appear asking that they upload a photo ID. Tell them that they may skip this step and move on to the next screen.

Participants are required to answer all of the questions in the PT reg form that have the single red-colored asterisk by them; questions that have two light orange-colored asterisks by them, such as the one asking to upload a photo ID, may be skipped.

The process will next present an authorization, consent, and release form. The patient (or patient's representative, such as parent or legal guardian) will click a box agreeing to their electronic signature, and then sign (type their name) to indicate that they consent to the PCR test and authorize the release of the test results to the project leaders.

IMPORTANT: As an added layer of data protection, iPads are set to time out after 15 minutes of inactivity. In case the iPad times out either while a participant is using it, or when Field Assistants are using it, the password to start the iPad up again is: **covid19** (all lower case). This password is also taped to all of the Field Assistant clipboards.

Qualtrics Questionnaire

Once the participant has submitted their PTReg information in the iPad, a message will appear at the end of the process saying "Please continue to this survey," beneath which is the hyperlink in blue that reads 'Survey Link' (Figure 9). The participant will need to click on it to progress to

the Qualtrics questionnaire. The first page will be an informed consent form for conducting COVID-19 antibody testing and the questionnaire; clicking “next” to progress to the questionnaire indicates consent. If someone decides to halt participation at any point, the Field Team should record partial completion of the survey for that household. Please note that participants may terminate their participation at any time, should they not wish to continue. Additionally, if there is a question they prefer not to answer, they may skip that question and continue through the rest of the questions.

The questionnaire link that was provided to Field Assistants for piloting the survey is the link to the most current and up-to-date questionnaire. It is provided here in case you wish to review it before your field work:

The initial information on the Qualtrics questionnaire auto-populates some of the information the participant has already entered while completing the PTReg. This includes the Sample ID (patient registration number), and basic demographics (year of birth, gender, race, and ethnicity). If the Sample ID is not pre-populated, the Sampler should provide the barcode number from the sample tube.

During inclement or cold weather, the participant may step into their house to complete the questionnaire. If the wifi connection is not strong, they may need to also take the MiFi with them.

A few things to mention to the participant:

- It will be helpful if participants have their calendar or perhaps access to their emails, to reference these when the questionnaire asks for dates of COVID-+ tests.
- If vaccinated and the participants have their vaccination card handy, or an on-line record of their vaccination dates, they can enter the dates precisely from these. If they don't have precise dates, **remind participants that estimates are ok.**
- Point out the forward and backward buttons on the iPad. If participants wish to go back to reread a previous question, and reenter a different response, this is allowed. **If they wish to skip any questions, they may move forward to the next page.**
- Some participants may need to be shown how to enter information by using the keyboard, or may need additional assistance navigating the iPad or the questionnaire. It is all right to provide assistance when requested, making sure to remain socially distanced except when passing the iPad back and forth.

- If participants request assistance, such as having you read out questions to them and marking their responses, you can do this. Remember to protect their privacy and you can remind them that they may skip any question.
- If participants decide they do not want to continue with the Qualtrics questionnaire, **you may let them know this is ok, and that they may still provide a sample for PCR testing if they completed the Patient Registration form.** In this situation, the Recorder should mark this on the barcode tracking sheet comments.

Once participants are done with the questionnaire, the Recorder will take the iPad back, and ensure the questionnaire has been submitted. The Sampler can now help the participant to collect their nasal swab (next section). If there are more participants to sample in the HU, the Recorder pulls up the camera icon in preparation for scanning the bar code of the tube for the next individual. Once all HU participants have completed the questionnaire, the Recorder will wipe down the iPad with a sanitizer wipe in preparation for the next HU visit.

Trouble-shooting the MiFi device, recharging, and powering off

Each team's MiFi has been connected to their iPad with its associated password in advance of your field work. In the unlikely event that the iPad asks for the MiFi's password, then this information is available in several places: it is written on a sticky note that is taped to the back of the MiFi, it is taped to the team's two clipboards, and it is also available by navigating to the Device Info window of the MiFi (Figure 5). [REDACTED] also have this information .

If the Recorder experiences any difficulties with the MiFi, please contact [REDACTED] to ask for assistance. The most predictable issues will be that the MiFi signal isn't being detected by the iPad, either because there is no cellular reception/unstable local signal in the neighborhood (see off-line plan below), or the device may be either too far from the iPad, or structurally blocked, in which case you may have to move it closer or alter the position of the device. For the frequency at which it has been set (2.4 GHz) it has a range of 10-15 meters, and it should be capable of permeating some structures such as doors and walls. For the type of work we are doing, it has been advised to use the MiFi at the 2.4 GHz frequency.

If the MiFi isn't responsive, and you've tried repositioning it, you may try rebooting the device by pressing the 'Power' button for approximately 8 seconds. Additionally, it has been reported that the MiFi may freeze up. In the unlikely event that this happens, it is advised that you pop out the battery and reseat it back into the device. If the MiFi is still not functioning, contact [REDACTED] for further assistance. Please call us if you are experiencing delays due to the MiFis and we will try to help you with troubleshooting.

Keep an eye on the battery capacity icon and if the device needs recharging, you may recharge it using the USB recharger in the fleet vehicle. To charge, connect the USB cable to the vehicle's charger and the other end into the MiFi Type-C Port. When the battery capacity is lower than 20%, the icon will appear red.

To power off the MiFi when you are done for the day, depress the Power button for 3-5 seconds. A message appears on the screen saying "Powering Off." If you depress this button for too long (around 8 seconds), you may accidentally reboot the device and it will turn back on.

Please be aware that these devices are not waterproof, so you need to protect them from snow and rain. Do not ever remove the SIM card.

No Cellular Reception Back-up Plan: Paper-and-Pencil PTReg and off-line Qualtrics App

In the event there is no cell service at the time of the visit to the household, Paper-and-Pencil Patient Registration (PTReg) forms will have to be completed. The Field team must hand write the associated sample bar code number on each form. The Qualtrics App will then be used for the Qualtrics questionnaire administration (Figure 10). The Recorder will have signed into the App using their [REDACTED] Single Sign On (SSO) in the morning before heading into the field, and download the survey using [REDACTED] wifi. The App can record survey data offline, and then syncs when it reconnects to wifi.

Once ready to open the Qualtrics App, the COVID Community Surveillance Survey appears (Figure 11). Click on the survey box to open up the questionnaire. You will then see a box open up that has a large green button that says "Take Survey" (Figure 12). Click on the green bar to pull up the survey.

When using the Qualtrics App, the screen that first appears in the survey will be the first page of our questionnaire with the consent information. A small window overlaying this may appear, saying "Location Unavailable" (Figure 13). If this happens, click OK. You may now pass the iPad on to participant to read the consent information, and advance through the questionnaire.

After the participant consents (by moving on to the next page), the first question on the Qualtrics questionnaire will ask for the Sample ID (Figure 14). The Sampler should read off the participant's tube bar code to be typed in here. The Recorder may need to assist some participants with this process. Please take extra care to ensure the bar code number is entered correctly. It should match the one on the tube that will be used to collect the participant's nasal sample, and also match the number the Field Team entered by hand on the paper-and-pencil PTReg form.

Note that in the absence of wifi, the sample bar code is entered as the Sample ID into the Qualtrics survey. This is different when wifi is working, and the Recorder scans the QR code that brings up the on-line PTReg form. In the latter case, the patient registration number auto-populates as the Sample ID.

Please remember that use of the off-line Qualtrics App is ONLY to be done when the wifi isn't working, and you are unable to scan the QR code and register through the on-line system.

Collecting biological specimens

Introduction

It is important to take precautions whenever collecting and handling biological specimens. Wearing appropriate PPE, social distancing, following appropriate sterile technique, and using sterile swabs all play a role. Parents or guardians will play an important role in helping to collect samples from young children.

Nasal Swab Specimen Collection: Instructions and materials

While approaching each household, Sampler will carry a tote bag containing:

- lidded transport cooler (Figure 15) containing:
 - 1 styrofoam rack, one 'clean' side holding tubes containing media only, a 'dirty' side where tubes containing nasal swab samples will be placed once collected
 - paper toweling (in case of any tube leakage)
 - 2 mini ice packs
- 1 Disposable lab coat for Sampler to don and doff the entire day
- 1 Face shield for Sampler
- Sterile nasal swabs and nitrile gloves
- Bottle of hand sanitizer (for Field Staff to use to sanitize their hands between HUs)
- Plastic zip-lock bag that serves as garbage transport (1 per HU)
- Styrofoam rack that Sampler uses to hold the participant's tube while they complete the consent and questionnaire
- Spill control kit (spray bottle of QT Sanitizer, absorbent towels, plastic garbage bag)

Additional materials will be carried in a separate tote bag by the Recorder:

- Spare nitrile gloves and masks
- Hand sanitizer wipes (for sanitizing iPads)
- iPad with recharger
- MiFi with recharger

- Document Folder containing—
 - Emergency Contact List (Appendix C)
 - News Media Handouts (Appendix D)
 - Door hangs (Appendix F)
 - Leave-behind print materials for participants (Appendix G)
 - Hard copy PTReg forms in case unable to connect to wifi (Appendix H)
 - Field Assistant Materials Checklist (Appendix M)
 - ‘Quick Guide’ summary of one day of Field Events (Appendix N)
 - Spare hard copy of Field Manual and Appendices
- 2 Clipboards (one for each neighborhood) to which the following are attached:
 - Housing Unit (HU) tracking sheet (Appendix A)
 - Tube Tracking Spreadsheet (Appendix B)
 - Neighborhood Map
 - Emergency Contact list (taped to the back)
 - Important passwords for MiFi and iPad (taped to sticky note on front)
- Pencils and pens including Sharpie for door hangs, twist ties for biohazard bag

The Field Assistants should stand 6 feet away from the participants during informed consent, questionnaire administration, and nasal swab collection, except when they are handing off supplies (iPad, nasal swab, etc). The Team Sampler will briefly summarize the steps the participant is to follow, taken from the ██████████ COVID-19 Community Surveillance Self-Swab Protocol (Appendix I), and provide verbal guidance with each step.

Nasal sample collection steps (following Protocol in Appendix I):

- Sampler dons gloves, lab coat, and face shield. Mask should already be on and stays on.
- Sampler prepares materials, including bar-coded tube, sterile nasal swab in unopened packaging, and hand sanitizer.
- Sampler places the bar-coded tube that has been already scanned into an empty Styrofoam holding rack used solely for this purpose, while the participant completes their questionnaire. This **must** be the same tube that was used to scan the QR code for this participant’s Qualtrics questionnaire.
- Sampler opens the swab at the stick end (keeping the fuzzy swab head inside the sterile packaging) and instructs participant not to touch the fuzzy end of the swab, nor allow it to touch anything else. Sampler holds packaging out stick-end protruding, allowing the participant to pull the swab from the packaging. Sampler steps back to maintain 6’ distance. Sampler discards the packaging in ziplock garbage.
- Participant should insert the swab into each nostril, just into the front of the nose. No resistance should be felt. It should not be painful. If they feel discomfort, they may have inserted the swab too far.

- Participant should swirl the swab around the nostril in circular motion for a count of 10 (Sampler will count down from 10) and then repeat in the second nostril, taking care not to let the tip touch anything during transfer to the other nostril.
- While participant is collecting their sample, the Sampler uncaps the participant's tube and replaces it in the Styrofoam rack. The rack may be placed on a table nearby if one is available, or on the ground, until ready for use. There is no need for the participant ever to handle their tube; it remains in the Styrofoam holding rack.
- Sampler asks participant to place swab fuzzy-end first into the uncapped tube that is in the holding rack, such that the tip is immersed in the media in the tube, taking care that it doesn't touch anything else. Participant then steps away from the tube and rack.
- Sampler retrieves the rack and breaks off the end of the swab at the scored location, taking care not to splash the liquid (holding the cap over the tube opening; see Appendix I photo). Tube is securely capped and placed in the "dirty" rack inside the transport cooler box. Sample must stay cool until delivered to CCTL test site.
- Field team offers the participant hand sanitizer if they wish.
- All trash (swab end, swab packaging, alcohol wipes, gloves) goes into clear ziplock bag that is transferred into the biohazard bin back at the vehicle.
- Sampler changes gloves only between HUs.
- Both Sampler and Recorder sanitize their hands using Purell between HUs.

If another person in the household is participating, the Recorder will then proceed to scan the next sample tube and have the next participant complete the PTReg, Qualtrics questionnaire, and sample collection process. The cycle continues until everyone in the HU has completed the iPad PTReg, questionnaire, and has been sampled.

Once everyone in the household has completed the survey, the Recorder wipes down the iPad and places the wipe in the garbage. All garbage from the HU should be placed in a clear ziplock bag. This bag is returned to the vehicle where it is transferred into the biohazard waste bin that is kept in the vehicle at all times.

Summary of PPE use and Hand Sanitization

Masks are to be worn at all times by all field assistants. Gloves should be worn anytime samples or waste are handled. Gloves need to be changed between households, or anytime they are ripped or torn. Purell alcohol sanitizer should be used to sanitize hands once gloves are removed. Face shields and lab coats are donned and doffed around the time of specimen collection by the Sampler only. Lab coats are discarded in biohazard waste at the end of the day, and shields are sanitized on an as-need basis, such as if a splash occurs during sample collection. iPads should be wiped down using individually-wrapped sanitizer wipes between households, as well any pens or pencils that are used by the participants. Both Field Assistants should sanitize their hands at the end of each HU visit.

Spill Control Procedure

In the event a tube leaks, spills, or drops, a team member will clean up the spill according to the protocol in Appendix J using the Spill Control Kit. Ask the participant to provide a new sample. **Use a Sharpie to draw a line through the bar code of the spilled tube, and note the bar codes of the spilled tube and the new tube on the Tube tracking sheet (Appendix B).** [REDACTED] will change the bar code number in PReg and in the Qualtrics survey. **Please review Spill Control Protocol (Appendix J).**

Ending the home visit

Once all participants complete the questionnaires and sample collection, ask the participants if they have any other questions or concerns. If it hasn't already been discussed, the team should communicate the timeline for the PCR test result for active infection. Test results will be available within 72 hours on the [REDACTED] portal. The participant only receives their results for active infection (PCR). Previous infection information (antibody results) is made publicly available at the aggregate community level, (i.e., percent of people with antibodies), to be posted on our survey URL website. It may take 4 to 6 weeks for antibody results to be posted. Participants are also given Leave-Behind print materials, which includes instructions on how to access PCR test results on the [REDACTED] portal, our survey URL website, and contact names and numbers of members of our team. Finally, **thank them for their participation.**

Script for thanking participants

A sample script of what to say to thank participants when departing from the household is provided in Appendix F, Script 3.

Print materials presented to Participating Households

- Study Consent/Executive Summary
- Instructions on how to access [REDACTED] Portal for COVID-19 PCR results
- Self-Testing Flyer
- Healthy Neighborhoods Flyer

The Field Team members are encouraged to practice their introductions and to practice common responses to questions out loud prior to going into the community. It is also helpful to walk through the procedural steps. The Field Team should not memorize a script. However, practicing the flow of response to various situations and questions is helpful to allow for smoother interactions in the field. This will also be practiced during the in-person training.

Preparation for next Household visit

Return to Vehicle

Once back at the vehicle, field assistants will need to take care of the samples already collected, and prepare for their next home visit. Wear gloves whenever touching or handling any samples or garbage; once done, doff gloves and sanitize hands. Here is a list of tasks that will need to be performed:

1. Transfer sample tubes from transport cooler to large “dirty” cooler, wearing gloves
2. Place the ziplock bag containing garbage into the larger biohazard bag in the bin, wearing gloves. Do not dump waste out of bags. Place the entire bag into garbage.
3. Replenish transport cooler with new tubes and/or ice packs from “clean cooler” as needed
4. Sanitize materials:
 - iPads between households
 - Face shields (as needed)
 - Clipboards, pens/pencils (as needed)
5. Remove gloves, discard in biohazard waste, sanitize hands

PPE Changeover

Only the sampler will wear a disposable lab coat, which will be donned and doffed for collecting specimens. In between households, this can be folded and carried in a tote. This will be discarded with biohazard waste at the end of the day.

Replenishment of tote bag with other materials

On an as-needed basis, check tote bags to ensure you have ample supplies of items. There should be enough for both weekend days, but if you are running short call [REDACTED] and we will deliver more to you in the field:

- ‘clean’ sample tubes
- clean nasal swabs
- individually wrapped sanitizing wipes
- ziplock bags for garbage
- extra masks and gloves; disposable lab coat if dirtied due to spill
- leave-behind materials
- paper-and-pencil patient registration forms ([REDACTED])
- door hangs
- media handouts

Transport of Biological Samples

Containers for samples will already have appropriate labels but they are described here for your information. Containers carrying samples must display *EXEMPT HUMAN SPECIMEN* clearly on the outer box, along with biohazard symbol near this label. You will find this label both on the large cooler box kept in the vehicle, as well as on the small transport cooler box, because these cooler boxes will be carrying biological samples.

There are additional Department of Transportation (DOT) regulations requiring specific packaging of the samples while being transported in vehicles back to the laboratory. These include triple packaging (tightly capped tube, stored in racks kept inside a plastic bag along with absorbent toweling in case tubes leak or break, and inside a sturdy lidded large styrofoam cooler box). The lids on these boxes must be secured such that they remain in place in case of accident. For this purpose, these boxes will be kept inside a plastic lidded tub while they are in transit (Figure 16).

Waste

All garbage collected during the survey needs to be properly handled. This includes placing the plastic bags into the biohazard bin in the vehicle, lined with a red biohazard bag and labeled REGULATED MEDICAL WASTE on the outside of the bin (Figure 17). At the end of the day, disposable lab coats will also be added to the biohazard bag along with the other waste. This garbage will then be placed in the large biohazard waste container near the back door of [REDACTED] at the supply pick up/drop off location. Twist ties are available to ensure the biohazard bags are adequately closed for proper disposal before placing in the large container. [REDACTED] will be available to assist with this at the end of the day.

Start-of-Day / End-of-Day

Start-of-Day

Take-home COVID-19 Ag test. Depending on the COVID status of campus and community, Field Staff may be required to conduct an at-home antigen test before coming to work on survey day. This will be discussed during the in-person training, and if required, kits will be given out then.

[REDACTED]. As a student worker, you must complete the [REDACTED] prior to coming to campus, be sure to do this first thing in the morning. Your ID Swipe card might not work to access campus buildings if you haven't done this.

Pick up of Fleet Vehicle: The Fleet garage is located at [REDACTED]

[REDACTED] Fleet vehicles are available within 60 minutes of the

scheduled reservation start time (7:30 am). Only the authorized driver will be allowed to pick up, drive, and return the vehicle. You will enter your [REDACTED] and password into the Kiosk in order to obtain the key to the vehicle reserved in your name. There is a parking lot at the garage where you may leave your personal vehicle. Please bear in mind use of [REDACTED] Fleet Vehicles is for business use only, you may not use these vehicles for any other purpose. Vehicles should have full tank of gas upon pickup. If in the unlikely circumstance you will need to get more gas, there is a credit card specifically meant for this purpose in the glove compartment that you may use. It is not necessary to return the vehicle to the garage with full tank.

If you run into difficulty with the Kiosk computer outside of normal business hours, you may contact [REDACTED].

Pick up of Materials: Materials will be packed up in large plastic tubs and tote bags, ready for pick up at the [REDACTED] (for map, see Appendix L). Access to this door will require swipe cards, so be sure to have your Cornell ID card with you in case no one is there when you arrive. Remember that in order for your swipe card to work, you have to complete your [REDACTED]. The system automatically removes access until this is completed.

Teams will be assigned staggered start times to have the opportunity to meet with [REDACTED], review your materials, and set up your iPads. Field assistants will have already familiarized themselves with all materials during the in-person training. All of your materials will be labeled with your Team number. The Recorder will complete the Field Assistant Materials Checklist check the tote bags and bin to ensure your team has everything, as is listed in the Field Assistant Materials Checklist (Appendix M), checking off all of the items on this check-list prior to heading to your first neighborhood. [REDACTED] will assist with this process. The Sampler will open up the Qualtrics app on the iPad, and using their [REDACTED] Single Sign-On (SSO) Net ID and password, download the Qualtrics survey to have it available in case you experience wifi difficulties later in the day. [REDACTED] will assist with this process. Don't forget to put on your name tag to wear throughout the day.

End-of-Day

After leaving the last household at the end of your day, you will drop off your samples and supplies at the same drive-up location where you picked up your supplies [REDACTED] will be available to assist you. Please go through your check-off list to ensure you have ample supplies for the following day; this is the time to replenish. If it is your last day, please complete the check-off list to indicate you've returned all materials. Pay particular attention to the MiFi and iPad along with their rechargers, as these are easy items to leave behind in the vehicle. You may leave your name tags in your supply bag overnight or at the end of the second day, to store for any future field work you might do.

Once you have dropped the samples off at the vet college and replenished supplies for the next day, or turned in all of your supplies, please wash your hands thoroughly before leaving for the day. The fleet car driver will return the vehicle to the fleet garage, whereas the non-driver is ready to leave for the day.

Fleet Car Return –

Saturday PM: When you return the vehicle to the Fleet Garage Saturday evening, you do not have to use the kiosk. Park the vehicle, lock it up and keep the key for Sunday.

Sunday AM: When you return to the fleet garage Sunday morning, park your car, find your fleet vehicle, and start your day. There is no need to use the kiosk indicating you are taking the vehicle again. The vehicles have been signed out for both Saturday and Sunday.

Sunday PM: Once your weekend work is all complete, you will return the car to the Fleet garage, remove all additional possessions, and lock it up. You do not have to do any additional cleaning of the vehicle. Return the key to the Kiosk, where you sign in using your [REDACTED] and indicate END THE TRIP. Remember: It is not necessary to return the vehicle to the garage with a full tank of gas.

A “Quick Guide” summary of the events of a day in the field, in the order in which they occur, is provided in Appendix N.

Safety and Breaks

More on Personal Safety

It is important to remember that individuals may exhibit their uneasiness of masked strangers approaching their door in a variety of ways. Some individuals may respond with slamming of doors, profanities, or threats. Safety is of utmost importance. In situations where individuals may escalate, please respond respectively by not further engaging the individual and promptly return to your vehicle. Some de-escalation methods will be reviewed by [REDACTED] Crime Prevention staff during the In-person training. These include such techniques as treating others with dignity by showing empathy and respect, trying to see the world through their eyes, offering options from which they may choose, allowing time for decisions, and responding rather than over-reacting to heightened situations (depending upon the context, this might be by thanking them for their time, returning to your vehicle, and contacting [REDACTED] if necessary). You will have the opportunity to ask any questions about these during the training.

If a member of the Field Team believes their safety is being compromised, please call local law enforcement / 911 immediately. As mentioned above, a one page summary with important emergency phone numbers (Appendix C) has been taped to the back of the two team clipboards.

Field Staff should pay attention to general safety awareness, such as being aware of cars when walking along streets or in driveways, paying attention at cross-walks when crossing streets, and avoiding black ice and slippery walkways/ deep snow in freezing or snowy weather.

In case of an accident, such as slipping or falling, an EHS Incident Report form must be completed by one of the Field Staff team members. The steps are similar to those of an automobile accident described earlier, to be followed in this order:

1. Emergency safety calls depending upon need, such as 911 for ambulance, and/or police
2. Report to your Supervisor, [REDACTED], available by phone/text (see Emergency Contact List sheet; Appendix C). [REDACTED] will help complete step 3 below.
3. Complete EHS Incident Reporting (within 24 hours of the incident):
[REDACTED]

Eating, Drinking, and Rest Room Breaks

Per federal guidelines, all field assistants are to schedule a 30 minute lunch break between 11 am and 2 pm. If bringing food and drink, store these away from biological samples and biohazard materials. A separate backpack or lunch pail is recommended. Do not carry food in the tote bags meant for field survey materials. Schedule breaks in between household visits, rather than interrupting a visit. Prior to eating, best practice is to wash hands with hot, soapy water. If this is not possible, 60%+ alcohol hand sanitizer, provided to each team, is recommended. Maintain social distancing when unmasking while you eat. Teammates should stay together at all times. Please use discretion in selecting a location to go to for your break.

COVID-19 Community Surveillance Field Manual

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Figures

Figure 1. Housing Unit selection using Kth interval count. The figure shows the starting point on the Northwest corner of the aerial map, indicated by the red pin labeled 1. From here, in this situation using the established Kth interval of 5, the field team selects every 5th household, indicated by the yellow numbered circles. Note that the field team sticks to the inside streets of the census blocks and includes interior side streets in the interval count. The [REDACTED] COVID-19 Surveillance Project's goal is to target 8 HUs in the neighborhood to which Field Teams are assigned; not 12 as is shown here. The Kth interval will be specified for the neighborhood map you are given.

Used by permission from [REDACTED]

Figure 2. Housing Unit (HU) selection process, approaching the HU, and determining eligibility.

Figure 3. Parental Consent and Child Assent Process for any Minors (< 18 yrs of age).

Figure 4. Turning MiFi on and off. Message that appears when powering on the MiFi. To turn on, depress and release the Power button quickly (for turning off, depress and hold for approx. 3 seconds).

Figure 5. Orbic 2.4GHz wifi link as appears in iPad. It will read “Verizon-RC400L-XY. Orbic wifi Device Info is displayed on the device (Note that the wifi password is near lock icon). You should not need to enter the password if you use the same numbered MiFi device as your iPad, unless if for any reason the iPad needs it again. The password is also written on a sticky note taped to the back of the device, and on the sticky note taped to your team’s clipboards.

Figure 6. Scanning the tube's QR code using iPad camera brings up the link to open [REDACTED] patient registration system. Note the message that appears instructing you to open this link using Safari. Click on the link.

Redacted

Figure 7. [REDACTED] Patient Registration System PIN entry. The PTReg is open and ready for entering our study PIN number **15777**. Once Patient Registration is complete, a link (see next figure) will appear that takes participants directly to the on-line Qualtrics questionnaire.

Redacted

Figure 8. First Patient Registration screen that appears after scanning QR code and following the Safari link. Note Specimen ID is the sample tube's bar code number.

Redacted

Figure 9. Qualtrics survey link visible at completion of the patient registration form. Patient registration number shown here is what auto-populates the Qualtrics Sample ID.

Use of the Off-line Qualtrics App:

Figure 10. Appearance of Qualtrics off-line App on the iPad.

Redacted

Figure 11. Use of Qualtrics Off-Line App: Select Survey. Use the questionnaire that pops up (note that the date will be different from the date shown here). Click on the survey box to open up the questionnaire.

Redacted

Figure 12. Use of Qualtrics Off-line App: Take Survey. Appearance of iPad upon clicking on the survey box. Click on the green bar that says 'Take Survey' to pull it up.

Redacted

Figure 13. Use of Qualtrics Off-line App: Survey consent form. This is the screen and message that pops up after hitting green button 'Take Survey' (Figure 12). Click 'ok' and hand the iPad to participant to read the Consent Page.

Redacted

Figure 14. Use of Off-Line App: Entry of Sample ID. First question that appears after the informed consent page is the Sample ID. Assist participant with entering the correct bar code number. This number auto-populates with patient's registration number when wifi is on, but here we need to enter the tube barcode number. Always double check the number. Please point out to respondent the arrow buttons for moving forward or backward in the questionnaire (shown).

Figure 15. Transport cooler box containing 'clean' tubes to carry to households. All tubes have bar codes on them. Once collected, tubes with samples (aka 'dirty' tubes) will be placed on the 'dirty' side of rack, as labeled. Cooler box will have a biohazard label. Absorbent toweling is included in the bottom of the cooler box in case any spillage in transport between homes and car.

Figure 16. Large cooler boxes are packed into single plastic tub. Dirty cooler is positioned such that exempt human specimen and biohazard label are visible through the tub. Tub containing both cooler boxes remains in vehicle all day.

Figure 17. Regulated Medical Waste containing biohazard bag for transport of waste in vehicles. Bin remains in vehicle all day; waste is transported to it via small zip lock bags brought to the HUs. The biohazard bag along with its contents is discarded at the end of each day. It is closed with a twist tie and placed in the large biohazard waste bin in the alcove of [REDACTED] lab near back door where supplies are picked up/dropped off.

**Appendix A. Housing Unit (HU)
Tracking Sheet Page 1 of 4**

Community: _____ Neighborhood: _____ Team #: _____ Sampling kth interval (k= _____) Team Initials: _____ & _____
Date: ____/____/____ PIN: _____ Block #: _____

****Don't count buildings that are not HUs (schools, offices, group housing, etc), HUs that appear vacant, HUs with hostile signage, HUs with safety issues, or HUs that are inaccessible. These are skipped and not counted in your sampling interval.****

****Replace HUs that decline to participate, had no adult home after two visits, or were excluded. Count another k HUs.****

Housing Units (HUs) Sampled 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14

APPROACH OF HU (select all that apply)

Door was answered	☐													
Declined to participate	☐													
No adult home after ...	☐													
1 st visit	☐													
2 nd visit	☐													

HU EXCLUDED due to...

safety issue after approach	☐													
isolation/quarantine	☐													
not their usual residence	☐													
language barrier	☐													
unable to obtain consent	☐													

PT Registrations Completed in HU: _____

Qualtrics questionnaires Completed in HU: _____

Nasal Swabs Collected in HU: _____

Community: _____ Neighborhood: _____ Team #: _____ Sampling kth interval (k= _____) Team Initials: _____ & _____
 Date: ____/____/____ PIN: _____ Block #: _____

****Don't count buildings that are not HUs (schools, offices, group housing, etc), HUs that appear vacant, HUs with hostile signage, HUs with safety issues, or HUs that are inaccessible. These are skipped and not counted in your sampling interval.****

****Replace HUs that decline to participate, had no adult home after two visits, or were excluded. Count another k HUs.****

Housing Units (HUs) Sampled 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24 25 26 27 28

APPROACH OF HU (select all that apply)

Door was answered	☐													
Declined to participate	☐													
No adult home after ...	☐													
1 st visit	☐													
2 nd visit	☐													
HU EXCLUDED due to...														
safety issue after approach	☐													
isolation/quarantine	☐													
not their usual residence	☐													
language barrier	☐													
unable to obtain consent	☐													

PT Registrations Completed in HU: _____

Qualtrics questionnaires Completed in HU: _____

Nasal Swabs Collected in HU: _____

Housing Unit (HU) Tracking Sheet Page 3

Community: _____ Neighborhood: _____ Team #: _____ Sampling kth interval (k= ___) Team Initials: ___ & ___
Date: ___ / ___ / ___ PIN: _____ Block #: _____

****Don't count buildings that are not HUs (schools, offices, group housing, etc), HUs that appear vacant, HUs with hostile signage, HUs with safety issues, or HUs that are inaccessible. These are skipped and not counted in your sampling interval. ****

****Replace HUs that decline to participate, had no adult home after two visits, or were excluded. Count another k HUs. ****

HU Addresses and other notes

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____
6. _____
7. _____
8. _____
9. _____
10. _____
11. _____
12. _____
13. _____
14. _____

Housing Unit (HU) Tracking Sheet Page 4

Community: _____ Neighborhood: _____ Team #: _____ Sampling kth interval (k= ___) Team Initials: ___ & ___
Date: ___ / ___ / ___ PIN: _____ Block #: _____

****Don't count buildings that are not HUs (schools, offices, group housing, etc), HUs that appear vacant, HUs with hostile signage, HUs with safety issues, or HUs that are inaccessible. These are skipped and not counted in your sampling interval.****

****Replace HUs that decline to participate, had no adult home after two visits, or were excluded. Count another k HUs.****

HU Addresses and other notes

- 15. _____
- 16. _____
- 17. _____
- 18. _____
- 19. _____
- 20. _____
- 21. _____
- 22. _____
- 23. _____
- 24. _____
- 25. _____
- 26. _____
- 27. _____
- 28. _____

Appendix B. Tube tracking sheet

Check-in Sat Sun	Tube Barcode ID	Team #	Neighborhood	HU #	Sample Y/N	Date Collected	Check-out Sat Sun	Comments
☐ ☐							☐ ☐	
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Appendix C. Emergency Contact List

1. Personal safety / accidents requiring ambulance: 911

2. Police—

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

4. HIPAA Compliance Line

[REDACTED]

5. Vehicle accidents:

If an accident occurs with a fleet vehicle, first call 911 if need an ambulance, and call the local police department if another vehicle or person is involved.

Once pressing safety concerns are attended to, immediately let your Supervisor, [REDACTED], know about the accident.

Complete an Incident Report if any incident that occurs, including Motor Vehicle Accident, at

[REDACTED]

Lastly, if an accident occurs involving fleet car, you are asked to report to Fleet Garage by email at [REDACTED] as soon as you are able—see [REDACTED] in vehicle glove compartment for additional instruction on this process.

Appendix D. News Media Handout (Press Release)

PRESS RELEASE

[REDACTED]

Appendix E. Door Hangs

TODAY'S DATE/TIME: _____

Sorry we missed you! Your home was randomly selected for an opportunity to participate in the COVID-19 Community Surveillance Survey to help determine how many people have been infected by COVID-19 or vaccinated in your community. Your participation may help us better understand how to limit the spread of the pandemic in this area.

We will try to return on _____
at approximately _____.

Call if you wish to request a different time, learn more, or decline participation.

Script 1: Approaching household and first conversation

██████ colleagues at ██████████ discovered that the first 30 seconds of interaction with households are crucial to getting participants' attention and willingness to participate. We need to consider ways that might stimulate conversation with household members who answer the door. We will practice this more during our in-person training.

If door is answered by an adult resident of the HU

“Good morning, how are you? My name is ██████████; we are students at ██████████, and are in your neighborhood today to conduct a community survey about COVID-19 [show badges as you are speaking]. We hope that this survey will help the community learn more about how many people have been infected with COVID-19 and what types of activities may have a higher risk of becoming infected. Are you interested in hearing more about this survey?”

Act naturally and be yourselves. Not everyone will want to engage, no matter HOW pleasant we are, but it can't hurt to be friendly and open and engaging. Remind yourself of the value of what we are doing, even if others may disagree. If they say they aren't interested even before you have had an opportunity to explain the survey, don't take it personally. Respect their wishes. Say thank you to those not participating, and politely say goodbye. Record on the HU Tracking Sheet.

If door is answered by a minor, a babysitter, a neighbor or a visitor

If a child answers the door, ask whether there is an adult at home with whom you may speak. Similarly, if a babysitter or visitor answers the door and you discover they aren't a member of this household, ask if an adult member of the household is around and if not, leave behind a door hang saying approximately when you will return (perhaps try to see when the adult will be home and see whether you are able to make it back by then). If it is the 2nd visit an adult member of the HU is not there, that will be the last attempt and the HU will be replaced. Record on the HU Tracking Sheet.

Script 2: Informed Consent*Adult*

“The purpose of the project is to look at the overall infection rates county-wide, as well as the immune response to a natural infection or to COVID-19 vaccinations. Your household was randomly selected. Your participation will involve completing an iPad questionnaire and providing a nasal swab sample for testing for infection and antibodies. The nasal swab is not painful, it is from the front of the nose and may tickle or irritate your nostril. The questionnaire should take 10-15 minutes. Most of the questions are easy to answer and you can skip any questions that you don’t want to answer. The questions will ask about any previous COVID-19 infections, vaccinations, activities that may result in exposure to COVID-19, and your thoughts on how to prevent COVID-19. If, at any time, you do not wish to continue you may stop your participation for any reason. This project will provide you a COVID-19 PCR test; results will be available online, similar to results obtained after getting tested at the [REDACTED] sampling site. The antibody results obtained from your sample will also allow us to better characterize the immune status of our community, which will help the county develop recommendations for COVID-19 boosters and other prevention practices. Unfortunately, we won’t be able to share your antibody results with you because it is not an FDA-approved test. The overall percentage of people with infections and immunity will be made publicly available on a website that you may visit. Individual results will never be shared. We have provided you with a lot of information. Do you have any questions? Would you like to participate?”

Minor or individual with Challenged Capacity (use best judgement regarding amount of detail)

“We are conducting a survey about COVID-19 infections and vaccinations. We are wondering if you would like to help us. We would like to swab the front of your nose, and answer some questions on an iPad. Your parent or guardian (mom/dad) will help you answer the questions, and also help do the swab. It won’t hurt but it might tickle. From this swab, we will tell if you have COVID-19 now and if you have immunity – if your body can fight off the virus. Is there anything you would like to ask us?” Later, after answering any questions they have, perhaps check back in to say “We just told you a lot of information. Can you repeat what it is that we are asking you to do?” and assess. “Great, would you like to participate?”

Script 3: Thanking Households

“Thank you again for participating in this survey. This will provide valuable data about COVID-19 in our community, and this information will benefit everyone. We have a few items to leave with you, including information on how to access your COVID-19 results through the [REDACTED] portal, and the website where you may go to find aggregate community data summarizing immune status in our community. It will take approximately 1-2 months to complete all the antibody testing and make this information available. This packet also contains a copy of the consent form, and contact names and numbers in case if you have any questions you would like to address later. Additionally, we have flyers that the Department of Health has asked us to provide,” and hand the participant these materials.

Appendix G. Participant Leave-behind Print Materials

Study Consent

We are asking you to participate in a survey titled "**COVID-19 Community Surveillance Survey**", led by [REDACTED]

The purpose of this survey is to provide critical data on the level of COVID-19 infection and immunity in your local community, which will help public health leaders make informed decisions. This survey will take between 5 and 15 minutes.

We will ask you to provide information about your demographics, household, COVID-19 vaccination status, previous COVID-19 infections, COVID-19 prevention measures, and attitudes about COVID-19. Your household was selected at random, and **participation is voluntary. You may skip any question by clicking the 'next' button.**

Participation of children and adults with legally authorized representatives ("wards") : If you consent to your child (ages 2 and up) or ward participating in this survey and they agree, we will ask your child or ward to fill out the survey or for you to help them fill out the survey.

The **nasal swab you provided will be tested for COVID-19** by the [REDACTED] COVID-19 Testing Laboratory in partnership with [REDACTED] for COVID-19 infection by PCR, and **it will be tested for COVID-19 antibodies by** [REDACTED]. **Your PCR test results will be available through** [REDACTED]. Positive PCR results will be communicated to the [REDACTED] Health Department. Positive samples may be sequenced, this data will NOT be returned to you. **The COVID-19 antibody results will NOT be returned to you,** [REDACTED] because the antibody test used is not FDA approved. However, a report of the aggregated data will be made publicly available.

Identifying information collected during the COVID-19 PCR test registration process will be securely stored by [REDACTED]. **Identifying information is not shared with** [REDACTED] **unless you opt-in to future studies**, then your contact information will be shared. **The unique code on your nasal swab tube will be used to link the COVID-19 test results and your anonymous survey answers.** Despite these measures, we cannot guarantee anonymity of your personal data. The anonymous nasal swab sample and survey information may be used in future studies and shared with other researchers.

If you have questions, please contact [REDACTED]. This project is paid for by the [REDACTED] and is supported by the [REDACTED]

Proceeding to the survey indicates your consent to participate or your consent for your child or ward to participate.

Executive Summary

COVID-19 Community Surveillance Executive Summary

The [REDACTED], in partnership with [REDACTED] Health department and [REDACTED], is conducting community surveillance for COVID-19. Surveys will be administered over the course of two or three select weekends in 2022. The purpose of this surveillance is to look at the overall infection rates county-wide, as well as the immune response to a natural infection or to COVID-19 vaccinations. Individuals from randomly selected households in the community will be tested to identify current infections with SARS-CoV-2 virus, measure antibody responses to natural infections or vaccine administration, and they will be asked about their COVID-19 knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. Local municipalities may use this information to guide their COVID-19 response, including recommendations for social distancing, mask wearing, school and business activities, or for the planning of vaccination booster administration to community members. De-identified, aggregated data on the prevalence of infection and immunity will be made publicly available.

Aggregate data for this project will be posted at the following URL:

[REDACTED]

Any questions about this survey, you may contact:

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

How to View Your Results Flyer

Redacted

**Appendix H. [REDACTED] Off-Line Patient Registration (PTReg) for
Community Surveillance Study Participants**
Paper and Pencil form to fill when there is no wifi

Redacted

Appendix I. [REDACTED] COVID-19 Community Surveillance Self-Swab Protocol

Title: Observed Self-Swabbing Protocol

Page 1 of 1

Observed Self-Swabbing Protocol

1. The purpose of this chart is to provide a standardized protocol for observed self-swabbing of COVID-19 community surveillance participants

2. **EQUIPMENT**
 - 2.1. Required personal protective equipment (PPE) for Observers:
 - 2.1.1. Face mask
 - 2.1.2. Face shield, goggles, or safety glasses
 - 2.1.3. Disposable gloves
 - 2.1.4. Long sleeve disposable lab coat

3. **PROCEDURE** When participant is ready for swabbing:
 - 3.1. Uncap tube and place uncapped tube back into empty Styrofoam rack near participant
 - 3.2. Hand stick end of swab to participant. Step 6 feet away from participant
 - 3.3. Instruct participant to insert swab end of stick into nostril and swirl interior in a circular motion
 - 3.4. Participant should not feel discomfort - if so, they have inserted the swab too far
 - 3.5. Monitor participant self-swabbing to count of ten for each nostril
 - 3.6. Ask participant to place swab in uncapped tube
 - 3.7. Retrieve tube. Hold cap over edge of tube while breaking swab - see photo for hand placement
 - 3.8. Securely recap tube and replace in transport cooler containing ice packs

- 3.9. Upon return to vehicle, place the sealed and labeled tube containing the swab in larger, labeled cooler that contains ice packs. Keep the sample cooled until it is brought to the [REDACTED] laboratory drop-off site.

Reviewed and Approved by : _____

Date:

Appendix J. COVID-19 Community Survey Spill Control Protocol

Title: Spill Control Protocol

Page 1 of 1

Spill Control Protocol

1. The purpose of this chart is to provide a standardized protocol for the handling of any tube spills or leaks while conducting of COVID-19 community surveillance fieldwork

2. EQUIPMENT

2.1. Required personal protective equipment (PPE) for individual cleaning the spill:

- 2.1.1. Face mask
- 2.1.2. Face shield, goggles, or safety glasses
- 2.1.3. Disposable gloves
- 2.1.4. Long sleeve disposable lab coat

2.2 Spill Control Kit (see photo):

- 2.2.1 Spray bottle with disinfectant (QT-Sanitizer)
- 2.2.2 Absorbent Towels
- 2.2.3 Plastic Zip-lock Garbage Bag

3. **PROCEDURE** When a tube spills,

- 3.1. Don PPE and gather supplies
- 3.2. Cover the spill with absorbent material (towels)
- 3.3. Spray the spill area well with disinfectant, covering the entire spill
- 3.4. Add dry paper towels to the perimeter of the spill
- 3.5. Wait 2 minutes
- 3.6. Place towels into plastic ziplock bag
- 3.7. Reapply disinfectant to the spill area.
- 3.8. Wait 2 minutes
- 3.9. Wipe up with paper towels, dispose in plastic ziplock bag
- 3.10. Press bag gently to zip closed, taking care not to expel air from bag into face
- 3.11. Remove gloves, sanitize hands, and don new gloves if necessary
- 3.12. When returned to vehicle, place ziplock bag into biohazard bin

Appendix K. Location of the [REDACTED] Fleet Garage.

Redacted

**Appendix L. Map of location of [REDACTED]
[REDACTED] Supply Pick-up / Drop-off**

Redacted

Appendix M. Field Assistant Materials Checklist

In preparation

Appendix N. 'Quick Guide' Summary of One Day of Field Events

Events that occur in the field occur in the following order. All protocols may be found here in the Appendices of this Field Manual.

- Start of day activities
 - complete tasks discussed during In-person training prior to reporting to campus
 - [REDACTED]
 - Home Ag test
 - pick up fleet vehicle
 - collect supplies [REDACTED]
 - complete supply checklist, set up iPad offline Qualtrics App, test MiFi
 - drive to assigned neighborhoods, start approaches to HU around 10 am
- Identifying and approaching households
 - start with Neighborhood A (approx. 10a – 12:30p); Neighborhood B (~1-3:30p); reverse this the next day to start with Neighborhood B first
 - Recorder marks location of selected “kth” households on housing unit tracking sheet
 - turn MiFi on and make sure iPad is connected to wifi prior to approaching the household
 - greet potential participants of the randomly selected households
- Obtaining informed consent
 - describe the survey purpose, participation requirements, risks and benefits
 - invite household residents to participate
 - screening process: determine eligibility
 - obtain consent
- Participant Registration and Questionnaire administration (Recorder)
 - scan QR code using iPad camera; record in tube tracking sheet
 - participant fills out patient registration (PTReg) form for [REDACTED]
 - participant completes the Qualtrics study questionnaire on iPad
- Specimen collection (Sampler)
 - Use PPE
 - demonstrate process, then guide participant through
 - nasal swab goes into correct participant tube
 - tube number cross-checked against tube tracking sheet
 - gather waste into ziplock bag
- Departing from households, moving on to next household
 - answer any questions, complete any record-keeping
 - thank both participants and non-participants for their time
 - ensure leave-behind materials are provided
 - return to vehicle if necessary, transfer samples, sanitize where necessary
 - replenish supplies, move on to the next Housing Unit (HU)
 - move on to Neighborhood B after lunch
 - if booked any return visits at the end of the morning or afternoon, try to return to these homes
- End of Day Activities— stop before it gets dark out (~4 pm)
 - return all samples, coolers and waste to [REDACTED]
 - replenish totes for next day of survey, or return supplies at end of survey
 - complete the end of survey supply checklist (Sun); check out with [REDACTED]
 - complete the Tube tracking sheet; review with [REDACTED]
 - return fleet vehicle to the garage to park overnight (Sat) or return to Fleet (Sun)